

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENHANCING
LANGUAGE LEARNERS‘ PROFESSIONAL SKILLS IN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. The study of the topic of the development of communicative abilities is pertinent today due to changes in current education. Three areas where socioeconomic changes are affecting education include unrestricted personal growth, creative initiative, and student autonomy. The relevance of researching the process of developing communicative competence is determined by the subjectivity, individuality, and psychological readiness of university students for intensive communication activity in the context of business communication, as well as the dearth of adequate scientific elaboration of this issue in pedagogy. It is crucial to do educational research in this regard to find effective methods for fostering communication abilities.

Key words: competence, communicative competence, social competence, social and political awareness, communication skills.

The Council of Europe has identified five main competencies that ensure that graduates of different educational institutions are prepared to adapt to and realize themselves in the demands of the labor market in the modern Information Society. These competencies are sociopolitical, informational, communicative, sociocultural, and readiness for education throughout life. It is undeniable that each of these abilities is intimately related to the others, but at the same time, a differentiated understanding of each competency's uniqueness and core is based on how it was formed. The interpretation of the powers put forward at the Berne symposium shares many similarities with the readiness and skill notions used in regional science. These abilities are described in depth below.

1. Socio-political competence. The key to this skill is the ability to make independent decisions while still being willing to solve difficulties and accept advice. This enables a person's psychological preparedness to respond to the environment, an active stance, and the capacity to pinpoint the core of the issue to swiftly settle personal, academic, productive, and social problems, as well as avoid them. To do this, it is required to develop fundamental reflexive abilities, follow specific activity algorithms, and learn to model a variety of problem tasks during the interactional educational process.

2. Information competence. The following are included in this competency as structural tasks: The essence of this competence is defined as the sum of willingness and need to work with modern sources of information in the realms of professional and daily activities, as well as a set of skills.

Find the necessary information from a variety of sources, including contemporary multimedia tools; assess its level of validity, novelty, and importance; process it in accordance with the situation and tasks; archive and store it; and use it to address a variety of issues.

3. Communicative competence. The three components of language, speech, and socio-culture are combined in the existing local and general European definitions of this ability. In practically every industry, effective communication is crucial for professional success and career

advancement. In addition to being able to openly convey his thoughts in his native tongue, a person must also be proficient in at least one other language.

4. Socio-cultural competence. As mentioned above, this competence is considered as one of the components of communicative competence, but in the last studies it began to stand out as an independent concept, connecting it not with communicative skills, but with the desire and ability to live and interact in the modern multicultural world.

5. Capability to continue his study throughout his life. As the world's technological and informational landscape changes and different spheres of human activity develop, a good education today won't guarantee future employment success without systematic and ongoing personal growth and development. The outcomes of the work of specialists might be deemed unprofessional if they are not continuously upgrading their previously attained information and developed abilities, skillfully assessing situations, and monitoring changes in the legal documents governing their operations. Additionally, it assumes that everyone should be psychologically ready to change their typical activity due to a variety of possible objective and subjective situations.

Thus, the process of forming a competent (competent) specialist involves the creation of a set of basic competencies. As can be seen from the above sources, a characteristic feature of a modern specialist is its communicative competence. A.K. Markova wrote that professional competence is an activity in which communication is carried out with a sufficiently high level of experience. It is noted that the changed conditions require changes in organizational processes and impose new requirements on the interaction between the members of the organization and their external groups [1, p.56].

It is argued that the concept of "competence" refers to a person's ability to communicate effectively with the environment. Interaction is an integral part of communication. In this context, communicative competence implies communication between subjects of professional activity, as well as knowledge, experience, forms of interaction, information exchange, carried out using language and specific information technologies.

In psychology, communicative competence is seen as one of the conditions of personal orientation. Communicative competence includes a set of knowledge, skills and skills that provide effective communication.

From the point of view of the theory and methodology of professional education, communicative competence is interpreted as a component of a generalized assessment of professional ability. A number of researchers (L. G. Antropova, L. V. Smirnova) characterizes communicative competence as an integral representation of an individual. L. G. Anthropova also adds that it is a professionally significant quality consisting of communicative knowledge, skills and skills; communicative orientation, humanistic position, communicative creativity [2, p.12].

Discussions about professional communicative competence in a foreign language have led researchers (O. Yu. Iskandarova) lead to the conclusion that this is a complex of personal characteristics, striving for which creates the best conditions for stimulating the educational and cognitive process, since it provides optimal psychological interaction in the process of professional communication in a foreign language [3, p.16].

Keeping in mind that communicative competence is the final result of the educational process, L.A. Petrovskaya offers specific forms of training for the formation of this personality trait [5, p.24].

E.V. Rudensky sees communicative competence as a manifestation of the subjectivity of an individual in communication based on a technological description [6, p.75]. According to the author, communicative competence is knowledge of the norms and rules of communication, awareness of the technology of application

(6, p.107). Communicative competence consists in the ability to make a socio-psychological diagnosis associated with the prospect of how the communication situation in which it is necessary to communicate occurs; programming the communication process, based on the specificity of the communication situation; "getting used to" the environment of a communication situation; the

implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communication situation [6, p.101].

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